

**County Center for Educational Resources and Assistance, Argeș
Centrul Județean de Resurse și Asistență Educațională Argeș**

**AsProEdu Association
Asociația AsProEdu**

**Personal Development International Conference
3rd Edition - Pitești 2023**

Book of abstracts

Ars Libri

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and Assistance, Argeş
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Mrs. Cristina MARIN – Inspector in the Romanian Ministry of Education

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SECTION A

Psychology, Development and Education

Moderators:

Ms. Mihaela LUNGU

Mrs. Camelia IOANAS

County Center for Resources and Educational Assistance Argeş

Personal Vulnerabilities and Human Trafficking

Dr. Silvia TĂBUȘCĂ, Romanian-American University
Expert in prevention of human trafficking and organized crime

Human trafficking is a serious crime that affects fundamental human rights and freedoms, often involving acts of torture and inhumane treatment. In recent decades, this crime has been considered a complex and constantly evolving international issue. The phenomenon is present everywhere in the world, in every habitable territory of the planet, with ascending forms in the developed states and in the poor areas of the world. Cases of human trafficking have been identified in the last 10 years in all territories of the world, except Greenland.

The exploitation of the human being by the trafficker is carried out for the purpose of economic or personal gain through various ways such as forced labor, sexual exploitation, begging and committing criminal acts, forced marriage or organ harvesting. Victims of human trafficking are often lured by traffickers with false promises of love and marriage, job opportunities, education or a better life in another locality/country. Once the victim comes under the control of the trafficker, their freedom is severely restricted, their fundamental rights are violated, and they are subjected to physical, sexual, psychological, emotional or economic-financial abuse. The consent of the victim does not remove the criminal liability of the trafficker because in a civilized nation no one can exploit another person and keep them in a state of slavery.

While vulnerabilities can vary widely among individuals, certain factors can increase the risk of their exploitation, such as: the existence of organized criminal groups, lack of education and awareness, demand for exploitation services, insufficiently trained or equipped authorities, corruption and impunity, globalization, migration and displacement, as well as poverty and gender inequality.

Most people around the world are not aware of the realities and extent of human trafficking and insufficient education hinders prevention efforts, leading to lack of proper victim identification and assistance. Lack of opportunities, limited access to education and unemployment increases the risk of trafficking. Women and girls are disproportionately affected by human trafficking, particularly in the context of sexual exploitation. Gender discrimination, social perception and norms, as well as unequal power relations contribute to their vulnerability. The ease of travel and migration brought about by the globalization often creates opportunities for traffickers to exploit people seeking better economic prospects or fleeing adverse conditions. Conflicts, poverty, natural disasters and political instability that generate migration contribute to the vulnerability of individuals. Migrants and displaced persons are particularly at risk due to their precarious situations and limited access to protection mechanisms on the territory of the state in which they are located. Addressing the root causes of migration can help mitigate the risks of trafficking, such as poverty and economic disparities that, also, create vulnerability to trafficking.

The demand for cheap labor, commercial sex, and other exploitative services creates an economic incentive for human trafficking globally. The demand for cheap labor in industries such as agriculture, construction and production fuels the exploitation of vulnerable workers. People who use the services of victims contribute to the perpetuation of this crime.

Human trafficking is often facilitated by sophisticated criminal groups operating across borders. They commit various illegal activities, and their operations are well organized, which makes it difficult to detect and dismantle them effectively and at the level of all cells. Strengthening the authorities for an effective and efficient response, strengthening international cooperation and promoting legislative reforms in line with the new ways of operation of criminal groups are essential to meet this challenge. Corruption or complicity within law enforcement agencies and other public institutions creates an enabling environment for human trafficking to thrive. In some cases, traffickers evade justice due to corruption or lack of resources to fight this crime. Many countries, including Romania, lack comprehensive legislation and effective law enforcement mechanisms to combat human trafficking. Inadequate and inconsistent legislation hinders the prosecution and punishment of traffickers and the protection of victims.

Keywords: vulnerabilities, human trafficking, organized crime, criminal groups, prevention.

CULTIVATING A GROWTH MINDSET IN EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract

In today's world, having a growth mindset is crucial in the light of ongoing changes. Students who possess a growth mindset understand that their abilities and intelligence can be developed with effort, learning, and persistence. Carol Dweck, a leading researcher in the field of motivation, describes mindset as a belief regarding the nature of one's characteristics. According to her research, a person with a fixed mindset avoids challenges, gives up easily, and sees effort as fruitless. On the other hand, a person with a growth mindset embraces challenges, persists in the face of setbacks, and sees effort as a path to mastery. They also find lessons and inspiration in the success of others.

Educators play a crucial role in developing a growth mindset in students. The goal of education is to help children develop a belief in their ability to learn and improve. This is achieved by creating high expectations for all children, regardless of their current abilities. The educators also aim to help children understand the nature of brains and intelligence, and how they can influence their own brain growth and development.

In our keynote session, we will showcase three practical examples of effective growth mindset interventions. These include initiatives tailored for early childhood education, primary school education, and high school education, each designed to nurture and amplify the power of a growth mindset in the formative years of our students. These interventions, named "Water Your Mind," "Construct Your Brains," and the "Growth Mindset Presentation," respectively, serve as concrete illustrations of how the principles of a growth mindset can be integrated seamlessly into various stages of education, equipping students with the mindset necessary for lifelong learning and growth.

Keywords: growth mindset, fixed mindset, school culture, positive education, students' motivation.

TEACHING FOR TOMORROW: THE GROWTH MINDSET AND CONTINUOUS LEARNING

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Objectives:

Emphasizing the significance of a growth mindset and continuous learning for educators in today's evolving educational landscape. Additionally, inspiring teachers to embrace these concepts for personal and professional growth, ultimately benefiting their students.

Material and Methods:

'Mindset: The New Psychology of Success', by Carol S. Dweck

'Adult Learning: Linking Theory and Practice' by Sharan B. Merriam and Laura L. Bierema

Results:

In today's changing educational landscape, teachers are taking on broader roles than traditional pedagogy. As educational methods and paradigms continue to shift and transform, it becomes increasingly evident that teachers must not only adapt but also proactively embrace the concepts of a growth mindset and continuous learning.

As defined by psychologist Carol Dweck, a growth mindset centers on the belief that abilities and intelligence develop with dedication and effort. In teaching, this mindset encourages seeing challenges as opportunities for personal and professional growth, fostering resilience, adaptability, and a willingness to experiment with new teaching methods.

Continuous learning is essential for teachers. It involves consistently improving knowledge, skills, and strategies to become better educators. Adult learning methods, like collaborative learning, reflective practice, and self-directed learning, support educators by recognizing their unique needs and experiences. These methods offer flexibility for tailored professional development.

Conclusions:

- A growth mindset and continuous learning are vital for educators to adapt and thrive in the changing education field.
- By exemplifying a commitment to continuous growth and nurturing their own professional development, educators become powerful agents of positive influence on their students.
-

Keywords:

growth mindset, continuous learning, educators, education, adaptability.

SELF-HARM: UNDERSTANDING, RECOGNITION AND INTERVENTIONS

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Objectives: The purpose of this presentation is to shed light on the multifaceted nature of self-harm, to understand its underlying psychological mechanisms, to recognize its signs, and to explore contemporary interventions.

Results: Self-harm encompasses a spectrum of complexities, from its motivations—which can include coping with overwhelming emotions, asserting control, self-punishment, and communicating distress—to its associated conditions, such as depression, anxiety, and borderline personality disorder. Prevalence statistics indicate a higher incidence among adolescents, with self-harming behaviors generally decreasing with age.

Conclusions: Modern therapeutic strategies, combined with proactive roles played by educators and social workers, can lead to more effective interventions and improved outcomes for individuals grappling with self-harming behaviors.

Keywords: self-harm, self-harm signs, therapeutic interventions

Motivation in the school organization, cause of conflicts

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Objectives:

An aspect of conflict and motivation might explore how these two elements intersect in the context of personal relationships.

Another aspect of conflict and motivation in the context of personal development might explore how personal obstacles and conflicts can be the engine of individual growth and improvement.

Material and methods

Thomas Edison's story shows that every failure and conflict he encountered motivated him to find innovative solutions and continue working on his invention. With each obstacle overcome, his motivation grew, and this cycle of conflict resolution and personal growth eventually led him to make a working light bulb.

Another example could be the story of J.K. Rowling, author of the famous "Harry Potter" book series. Rowling went through many conflicts and difficulties in her life, including periods of poverty and personal problems. However, these obstacles only motivated her to pursue her passion for writing. She wrote the first book "Harry Potter and the Sorcerer's Stone" during a difficult period in her life. It was rejected by numerous publishers before it was published. However, Rowling remained motivated and determined to pursue her dream of becoming a successful author. This motivation led to the creation of an exceptional literary and cinematic franchise.

Results:

Gandhi organized peaceful protests and marches to draw attention to injustices and gain India's independence. Despite violent repression from the British authorities, he continued to follow his principles and remain committed to his cause. Through his peaceful approach and intelligent management of conflicts, Gandhi contributed to India's independence in 1947.

Conclusions:

This story emphasizes the power of motivation in the face of serious conflicts and difficulties, and how peaceful and conscious approach to conflicts can lead to significant changes and the achievement of major goals in history.

Keywords: motivation, determination, success, conflict, negotiation, communication

Holistic Child Development - A Psychological Perspective

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Objectives of this paper: Presenting the concept of development from a psychological point of view.

Materials and methods: Qualitative literature research

According to Elizabeth Hurlock "Development is qualitative change. Development is the orderly, harmonious and progressive changes leading to the goal of maturity."

According to Skinner "The process of development is both gradual and continuous."

According to Crow and Crow "Change in the whole organism is development"

Types of Development: Physical development, emotional development, mental development, social development, moral development.

Social development: According to the Russian Psychologist Vygotsky, social factors affect the intellectual development of a child. A child learns to speak by observing the way people around him pronounce. That's why a child of Gujarati society learns to speak Gujarati and a child of Hindi speaking society learns to speak Hindi.

Emotional development: A child's emotional development begins at birth. An infant begins to establish a sense of belonging with the parent or caregiver. Social and emotional development begins with emotionality. Affection begins with the mother or nanny or any person in the family who takes care of the child and such an emotional relationship is called attachment.

Moral development: Ethical questions keep appearing in our daily life. The rules of social behavior that lead a person from bad behavior to good behavior.

Mental development: Mental development is a matter related to the development of the child's ability to perform various mental processes and intelligence.

Conclusion

Various factors affect the overall development of a child. In which from the perspective of psychology, it is seen to affect mental, social, emotional and physical as well as moral matters. Today's child is tomorrow's future in which the child's personality becomes socially useful by considering all aspects of the child's overall development. Considering the process of holistic development of the child gives an excellent personality to the family, society and nation.

Keywords: child development, personality, change.

Managing conflict in the school environment: promoting harmony and personal development

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In the school environment, conflicts can be an inevitable aspect of interactions between students, but also between students and teachers. How do we manage these conflicts and turn them into opportunities for learning and personal development?

One of the most significant keywords in the school environment is bullying, which is an extremely harmful type of conflict. Students can become victims of bullying and this can have long-term effects on them. Thus, schools and educators work hard to identify and prevent these situations, but also to provide support to affected students.

Another important approach is to promote "constructive conflict resolution"; in the school environment. Students must learn to communicate effectively, negotiate and find solutions to their conflicts. This process involves developing the skills of empathy and understanding, which can help create a more peaceful atmosphere in the school. Mutual respect is also essential to reducing conflict in the school environment.

Promoting respect between students and between students and teachers can help create a more harmonious environment.

Schools have also implemented conflict prevention programs, which can involve both social and emotional education and mediation for more serious conflicts.

In conclusion, conflict in the school environment cannot be completely eliminated, but it can be managed and used as an opportunity for learning and personal development. By fostering an environment based on respect, effective communication, and constructive conflict resolution, schools can help shape students into responsible and empathetic adults.

Keywords: bullying, conflict resolution, social and emotional education, communication, prevention.

WAYS TO ENHANCE PERSONAL GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT FOR TEACHERS

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Abstract:

This paper presents the role and importance of personal development of human resources in the pre-university educational system. Personal development is essential for all actors involved in the educational act and determines changes from the individual to the organizational level. It takes a lot of hard work and dedication to be an effective teacher. Like other careers, there are those who are more natural at it than others. Even those with the most natural teaching ability must put in the time necessary to cultivate their innate talent. Personal growth and development is a critical component that all teachers must embrace in order to maximize their potential. There are several different ways that a teacher can enhance their personal growth and development. Most teachers will use a combination of these methods to solicit valuable feedback and information that will guide their teaching career. Some teachers may prefer one method over another, but each of the following has been proven to be valuable in their overall development as a teacher. The teaching staff must face all the confrontations involved in the process of change at the organizational and educational level, but also in relations with others, as well as with themselves.

Key words: personal development, growth, educational system, organization, teaching career

EDUCATIONAL CONFLICTS

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Educational institutions serve as dynamic hubs of learning and personal development. Within these settings, a multitude of interactions occur among students, teachers, administrators, parents, and community members. These interactions, while often constructive, can sometimes lead to conflicts. To create a harmonious learning environment, it's crucial to understand the various facets of educational conflict, including its types, causes, and effective resolution strategies.

Educational conflicts can have diverse causes and, subsequently, both positive and negative consequences.

Causes: These conflicts often stem from factors like power dynamics, hierarchy issues, and differing perspectives among students, teachers, and administrators. They can also be influenced by broader issues such as ongoing military conflicts, which can disrupt labor relations within the education sector. This, in turn, can lead to tensions between school administrators and teachers, often due to communication gaps and varying management styles.

Consequences: The outcomes of educational conflicts can be twofold. Positive conflicts can stimulate healthy competition and growth among students, promoting their learning and development. However, negative conflicts can disrupt the teaching and learning process, potentially hindering students' educational progress. The advent of online education has added new dimensions to these conflicts, with issues like communication gaps and varying management styles further complicating the situation. Consequently, conflict resolution skills have become crucial to manage these issues effectively

Conclusion: educational institutions are dynamic crucibles of learning and personal development, where the flames of knowledge and growth shine brightly. In these educational crucibles, a diverse array of students, teachers, administrators, parents, and community members engage in a complex tapestry of interactions, encouraging the pursuit of wisdom. While these interactions often lead to productivity and enlightenment, they are not immune to occasional sparks of conflict.

Keywords: education, conflict, resolution, personal development.

PEER BULLYING PREVENTION AND INTERVENTION

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Objectives: School, with its protective and preventive dimension, it should try to prevent peer bullying by preventing problems before they occur, ensuring school, family and student cooperation, raising family awareness, and preparing the necessary intervention plans by seeing the need for change in other systems. While combating peer bullying at school, it should also lead to important efforts regarding the implementation and evaluation of prevention and intervention programs for peer bullying regarding the protection and development of mental health at school.

Material and methods: Peer bullying can be grouped in terms of implementation. Physical bullying such as kicking, slapping, pushing, pulling. Verbal bullying such as teasing, unpleasant name calling, and derogatory remarks. Emotional bullying can be indirect, such as creating and spreading gossip and rumors, excluding oneself from the group of friends and leaving one alone, or in the form of taking money or other belongings by force, threatening to take them, or damaging one's belongings. Socio - lifestyle-induced bullying among economically rich and poor students. Bullying among students related to academic success can be given as an example.

Results: It is important for children who are bullied to establish positive friendships in school life so that they can establish healthy relationships in the future. It was stated that the family and school staff exhibited negative attitudes towards the child who exhibited bullying behavior, did not approach the child with empathy and criticized him. The mental health needs and vulnerabilities of these children should not be ignored.

Conclusions: When creating intervention and protection programs regarding peer bullying, attention should be paid to the developmental period characteristics of children. School staff should know that peer bullying can occur in all schools, but that peer bullying is not a part of growth and development and that children cannot become stronger by being exposed to peer bullying.

Keywords: Peer bullying, aggression, prevention

ABOUT THE BOOK “THE END OF AVERAGE”

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In the late 1940s, the American Air Force had a serious problem. Too many planes were crashing. When the daily peak reached, 17 pilots had crashed. The pilots were held responsible. The engineers were confident that there was no problem with the aircraft's parts, and the pilots were confident in their piloting skills. They examined the cockpit features. Cockpit measurements were consistent with average human characteristics taken in 1926, but no research had been conducted since then. In 1950, the measurements of approximately 4000 pilots were taken and their averages were calculated. Everyone now believed that accidents would end, except for one person. Lieutenant Gilbert S. Daniels. Daniels was given the task of taking measurements of the pilots, but he always had the same question in his mind. “How many pilots are truly average?” Although Daniels stretched the concept of average as much as possible, the number of pilots who fit the term average pilot was ZERO.

Daniels was not the first to reject the idea of the average person. Dr. Dickinson said that by taking the measurements of many women and calculating the average, he found the measurements of the ideal, that is, normal woman. They built a statue of this woman and called her name Norma. In a contest held by the Cleveland Museum of Health, they were to find the woman closest in size to Norma. However, at the end of the competition, it was seen that no woman was of Norma's size. However, at the time, they interpreted this to mean that American women were misshapen.

What would it be like if the rest of society followed this change when the military realized that the concept of average was misleading? If there was a world in which each individual was evaluated on his own merits and not how close or how far we are from the current average? Even your financial situation is evaluated according to how much it deviates from the average.

Conclusion: The average is useful if you are comparing two different groups of people, but the average is useless when you need to make a decision about hiring an individual. There is no such thing as average body size, average intelligence, average character.

Keywords: average, concept, Air Force.

EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM IN POLAND

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Abstract

Education is one of the most important factors in economic growth. The development of education is a significant element of a state and the European Union policy. A lot has been done for the improvement of education quality and the increase in innovation since people realized how important education is. The EU policy, focused on the equalization of opportunities between all the Community states, creates conditions conducive to the development of education, delegating adequate financial and intellectual resources.

The article mainly aims to discuss the role and significance of the system of education in the contemporary world, especially taking into consideration the current situation in Poland.

The article is factual in character and it contains a review of current domestic and European documents concerning the system of education. Apart from that one part is devoted to a presentation and an analysis of statistical data.

The statistics used let the author present the situation in the Polish system of education against the background of other member states. The analysis conducted showing strengths and weaknesses of the Polish system of education should provide decision-makers with guidelines on financing and reforming education.

The research and conclusions presented constitute a contribution to further analysis and work in the field, enriching the knowledge of the system of education in Poland.

Keywords: strengths, weaknesses, educational system, educational reform.

Prejudices Regarding Human Resources Management

Prof. Marcu Jenica-Loredana

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Like any other field of activity, human resources management is characterized by certain prejudices. Adapting to the conditions of the market economy requires the elimination of such, because they can generate a series of unfavorable consequences that affect the activity of the entire organization.

The objective of this paper is to present to the public such preconceived notions and to explain the reality of human resources management.

The widely spread preconceived notions are:

The human resources manager oversees the entire staff;

Human resources administration is the “communist” version of human resources management

Human resources management is the appanage of psychologists

Human resources management is the appanage of economists

Human resources management is the appanage of lawyers

The best human resources specialists are those who use the most English terms

Performance evaluation and job evaluation are the same

Some of the leaders of Romanian organizations are not interested in human resources management because they are not well trained professionally

Anyone who has worked with people is good at human resources management.

The consequence that may arise in such cases is the low efficiency of such people, because the human resources manager must be able to evaluate their employees, having to carry out a series of technical works with economic justification.

Keywords: human resources, management, prejudices.

Human resources, the main concern of the organization

Prof. Marcu Dragoş Adinel

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The fundamental role of human resources at the scale of the entire society is also found at the level of the organization, a fact recognized and argued by numerous scientists from different countries and by the managerial practice of nationally competitive companies (*Content presentation in O. Nicolescu, I. Verboncu, The Fundamentals of Organizational Management*). Some specialists consider human resources to be the human capital of the organization.

Objectives of this paper are to dedicate a special subchapter to human resources management within the overall management of the organization also takes into account the fact that people are, along with information, the main raw materials of management.

Conclusion: By analysing the definitions developed by various scientists, it can be concluded that the main defining element of creativity is generating new ideas. Innovation, however, is characterized both by the emergence of new ideas and by making changes in the organization based on them.

Organizing activities aimed at human resources in an organization can be done in several areas: personnel, education, payroll, research. As a type of internal organizational structure of the human resources department, functional organization (structure) and matrix organization (structure) can be used. The human resources function includes all activities oriented towards the human factor, having the following targets: conception, design, optimal use, maintenance, socio-human development.

Human resources management is a set of measures regarding the recruitment, selection, employment, integration into the workforce, training, development and motivation of employees, until their individual employment contract ceases. What can be observed about each of the above-mentioned definitions of human resources management is that they are not contradictory, they complement each other instead.

Keywords: human resources, management, organization.

Solving Tomorrow: Problem-Based Learning in the Age of Innovation

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Problem-Based Learning is a powerful pedagogical methodology that focuses on student agency, problem-solving, and innovative creative practices to achieve intended learning outcomes and promote emergent learning. Significant challenges faced by educators in a wide variety of contexts have been identified and this methodology seeks to address, the following issues:

- Securing and holding student engagement
- Developing and managing a sustainable approach to teacher workload
- The desire to teach skills and values above knowledge and information.

These challenges were explored through a case study of a problem-based learning experience which involved students solving the problem of how to teach their own grandparents English. Students followed a general Design Thinking process over the course of 8 weeks as part of this problem-based learning experience.

As a result of this case study, and through considerable further refinement, exploration, iteration, and trialing, a mapping of some of the core considerations for successful problem-based learning experiences is established. Guiding principles of the developed methodology include:

- Teachers take on the role of facilitators in which they assist in resolving students' solutions rather than solving their problems.
- Allowing significant student choice and autonomy in the process fosters a strong sense of investment and ownership.
- Allowing for and encouraging emergent learning throughout the process that allows students to learn in a personal, self-directed way.
- Designing learning experiences that emphasize the development of skills and values above knowledge and information.
- Centering the learning experience on the engagement with and solving of a well-considered problem.

Through these processes educators can address the sustainability of teacher workload, the need to develop skills and values rather than knowledge, and offer learning experiences that hold and sustain authentic student engagement through problem-solving and student ownership of the learning journey.

PERSONALITY PROFILE IN DEPRESSED ADOLESCENTS

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The paper aims to demonstrate the effectiveness of the psychotherapeutic approach in the depressive disorder of the adolescent, emphasizing the importance of the methods and techniques used as well as the relationship between self-image and depression in adolescents.

Psychologically, adolescence is related to the activation of sexual instinct, the shaping of professional and social interests, the desire for freedom and autonomy, the amplification of emotional life. A series of these disturbances, searches, peculiarities of adolescents were captured in this paper.

OBJECTIVES: Making a portrait of adolescence, its particularities and psychopathology starting from theoretical data and presenting cases -Creating a model of psychotherapy and counseling of adolescents in difficulty; Studying the efficiency of counseling and psychotherapy approach in personal development and adaptation to the social environment of adolescents in difficulty.

METHODS The following tools can be used to evaluate the effects of treatment, which can be administered before and after therapy: BECK inventory for depression; Hamilton questionnaire, Family drawing test, PSDQ psychiatric screening and diagnosis questionnaire. In developing the therapeutic program, we used a method of combined techniques to test the relationship between the intensity of depression and the level of self-esteem of adolescents in case studies.

CONCLUSIONS Adolescence is a complex stage in human life, with exceptional dynamics in time, with multideterminations and Mult conditionings, related to the somewhat uncertain position that the adolescent occupies in the system of evolutionary periods of life.

Keywords adolescence, personality, depression, self-image, psychotherapeutic approach.

ADDRESSING ANXIETY THROUGH EXPERIENTIAL COUNSELING METHODS

(CASE STUDY)

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- (2) Liceul Teoretic Costești, Argeș, Romania
- (3) Grădinița cu Program Prolungit Fantezia Costești, Argeș, Romania

OBJECTIVES:

Development of skills necessary for lifestyle management, interpersonal relationship skills, self-regulation in relation to oneself and other people, self-knowledge and personal analysis in order to reduce anxiety.

INSTRUMENTS USED

Millon Clinical Adolescent Inventory (MACI); 2. Big Five Minulescu Questionnaire (ABCDM); 3. State-Trait Anxiety Inventory® Form for Children (STAIC); 4. Projective tests: Family Drawing and Tree Drawing; 5. Semi-structured interview; 6. Observation.

RESEARCH RESULTS:

Final results recorded low scores on the scales Insecurity in relation to peers, Lack of social interest, Childhood abuse, Body disapproval. A decrease compared to the initial scores was also obtained for Clinical Syndromes, the most important being: Eating disorders, Predilection for substance abuse, Impulsive tendencies, Anxious living.

Scales of Extraversion, Maturity, Agreeableness, Conscientiousness, Self-Actualization: they recorded slightly increased scores, which highlights the preference for activities with low energy consumption, the preference to remain in the background, but makes an effort to take the initiative, to adapt in interpersonal relationships. The scores of both scales of the STAIC (S-Anx and T-Anx) are located between medium and high, and this indicates that anxiety manifests itself almost universally in the adolescent's life.

CONCLUSIONS AND FINAL ASSESSMENTS

The results obtained at the end show that the Intervention Program based on experiential counseling techniques achieved its main objective, namely that of reducing the anxiety of the 15-year-old adolescent girl, confirming the hypotheses established at the beginning of the program.

Thus, analyzing the results obtained in the clinical tests applied pre- and post-intervention, it was observed the improvement of the scores of several scales of the instruments administered in the first stage of the program.

An important aspect that remains to be investigated in the continuation of the intervention program is the family environment, which has a major influence on the socio-emotional life of the adolescent girl and which leaves its mark on her lifestyle.

Keywords: anxiety, experiential counseling techniques.

HOW ARE THE IRISH ABLE TO MANAGE IT?

EXAMPLE OF GOOD PRACTICES IN THE IRISH SOCIAL CARE SYSTEM

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Objectives: The main objective of this paper is to present how the Social Care System from Republic of Ireland is dealing with some tough problems from the society (like violence and anti-social behaviors from a very young age, child abandonment, drug use or online violence) and how Ireland is trying to restore his Young People on the correct path. Lately, in the public space of Romania were presented some important cases of anti-social behaviors, which show us that the society is changing, and the change could take a negative shape. This paper aims to increase the awareness of the negative behaviors that could appear in the society and to present some good practices that one of the best social systems from the world is using.

Materials and methods: Working in the Irish Social Care System gave me the opportunity to use participatory observation in a very direct way. I also used qualitative literature research to confirm my observation results.

Results: Promoting some of the good practices from the Irish Social Care System together with the awareness of possible anti-social behaviors that could appear from an early age.

Conclusion: Republic of Ireland in the recent years has registered an increase in frequently of the anti-social behavior, especially in teenager population. However, with a good social system, good techniques and a lot of consistency they are managing to control and give to the Young People a platform for a good future perspective.

Keywords: social care, anti-social behaviors, young people.

CANCEL CULTURE – A PHENOMENON OF ASSERTING POWER AND CONTROL OR PAVING THE PATH TO SELF-IMPROVEMENT?

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(1) Virginia Andreea LUPU

(1) Centrul Județean de Resurse și Asistență Educațională, Argeș, România

Objectives: This paper aims at describing the phenomenon of Cancel Culture, present an objective analysis of its advantages and disadvantages, depict the current general opinion on the topic, emphasize who the main actors behind the scenes are and pinpoint less disruptive alternatives that could, instead of harming one or both parties, help upgrade peoples' communication skills, hence, lead to personal development.

Material and methods: The research is based on the analysis of scientific articles and Youtube videos on the matter.

Results: Cancel Culture has divided people into avid advocates and believers of a better way. The trend has raised a number of questions: does the quote your rights end where mine begin is heavily misunderstood and twisted into banning and condemning freedom of speech? Is cancel culture the new bully on social media turning people into persona non grata? Is cancel culture the output of not dealing with rage, anger, trauma, codependency? Do we continue to blindly harm ourselves in either calling someone out or in in the name of social justice? Is there a better way? How do we ensure the emotional and spiritual growth of both parties with minimum damage to each part?

Conclusions: Cancel culture started off as a way of dealing with dreadful, unethical behavior and speech, which within itself, is a good way of setting boundaries and not putting up with abuse. However, along the way, things took a wrong turn and now there is a new trend of 'cancelling cancel culture' for being detrimental to humanity. Many have come up with solutions all pointing towards considering this phenomenon an opportunity for each individual to develop a new set of skills and to upgrade our communication and relationships to ones based on compassion, faith in one another, empathy and, above all, love.

Keywords: cancel, culture, growth, development, society.

SELF EFFICACY, WELLBEING AND INITIATIVE FOR DEVELOPMENT AT STUDENTS

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The objective of this research is the study of the relationship between self-efficacy, wellbeing and the initiative for personal development in students.

Materials and Methods: The study of the relationship between self-efficacy, personal well-being and initiative for personal development in students based on their academic performance. The general hypothesis of this study is about the relationship between academic performance and self-efficacy, personal wellbeing and development initiative. The working hypotheses of this study is about the academic performance, if this performance declines, so do self-efficacy, personal well-being, and developmental initiative. The instruments used were SES self-efficacy scale, Riff psychological questionnaire, the psychological questionnaire for the personal development initiative, version II and the clinical interview with the help of 3 subjects who were interviewed about the concepts above.

Results: The proposed work aimed to develop an example of intervention, using valid tools to quantitatively measure the 3 dimensions studied in relation to academic performance so that the key, defining elements within these concepts can be highlighted. The obtained results correlated with the research hypotheses, with the general hypothesis, which is confirmed, but also with the working hypothesis.

Conclusions and final assessments: Self-efficacy, personal well-being and personal development initiative in the academic environment, in this case on academic performance among students is a separate concept that represents the bridge between success and failure. The conclusion following this route that I followed in the realization of the present work was the fact that the academic environment has an important role, as well as the familiar environment, as well as the socio-economic environment of which a person is a part. As long as there is optimal development, without discrepancies or significant differences, significant changes, significant results, the implementation of a healthy lifestyle can be achieved, the greatest gain belonging to the individual who will adapt, develop and reach his maximum potential.

Keywords: Efficacy, Wellbeing, Personal, Development, Students

PSYCHOPEDAGOGICAL COUNSELING IN THE CASE OF SCHOOL MALADJUSTMENT

Summary

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The article in question represents a psycho-pedagogical counseling plan to solve a case of school maladjustment. We are going to detail the step-by-step practical approach of this issue which is specific to educational counseling, on a study case of a student.

The objectives of the action plan: eliminating the cause, creating situations that will stimulate the feeling of responsibility and self-control (rehabilitation programme by socialization, motivating the child with the help of appreciations, rewards); school adaptation of the 3rd grade student through psychological knowledge of the personality profile; cognitive stimulation; psychological counseling of the child and his family.

Methods and materials: activities of remedial education with the student; collaboration and self-help in different activities; tight connection with the family. Tools: written evaluation, oral evaluation, practical evaluation, observation, activity products analysis.

Results: establishing some strict rules; his involvement in certain tasks to have different responsibilities; teaching some self-help and relationship abilities; the student's seat to be near a quiet student, that accepts his presence and helps him ;at the first desk , so that he doesn't bother the others , giving examples of positive deeds during classes.

Conclusion: the achievement of the initial aimed objectives, so after applying the psychopedagogical counseling plan (creating a favorable environment to communicate with the teachers and the classmates; participating in support activities and psychopedagogical counseling; efficient communication with the family and the people around) our student becomes a more attentive one, more responsible, he is loved and encouraged by his colleagues ;he managed to get understanding from the other students' parents . In conclusion, our subject handles better the beginning of the school year as a result of the psychopedagogical counseling.

Keywords: case study, student, learning difficulties.

CASE STUDY OF CYBER-BULLYING

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During the day, a teenager received a phone call from what appeared to be a real Romanian number and he was threatened to be physically harmed. Foul language was used as well. The young boy was frightened, but at the same time he was confident in telling his parents about this phone call.

Objectives: The main objective of this paper is to raise awareness concerning the phenomenon of cyber-bullying. This abstract is inspired from a real-life scenario when an adolescent was called with an app with a spoof number and he was seriously threatened.

Materials and methods: case study of a 17 years old teenager.

Results: The parents called the alleged number, but it turned out to be a person from another Romanian city, no link whatsoever with the situation. Both parents and the person whose number was spoofed alerted the Police regarding this incident. The Police advised all persons involved to file a complaint describing the situation. The aggressor/aggressors used a voice filter built within the app. The school principal and the classroom teachers were also informed about the situation in order to provide counseling. The teenager who was a victim of this threat was scared, however he was encouraged to inform his trustworthy adults if anything like this ever happens again.

Conclusion: Educating ourselves and our children about all this spoofing and scamming methods is a powerful tool for prevention.

Keywords: cyber-bullying, dangerous app, education, on-line safety.

APPROACHING ECOLOGICAL EDUCATION AND ECOLOGICAL CREATIVITY

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A comparative analytical approach of the three types of ecological education, formal, non-formal and informal, leads us to the conclusion that all these types of ecological education are necessary, but also complementary, their variability coming to meet the increasingly complex situations in which people are placed in contemporary society and that they can solve by creating viable solutions.

The main objective of this paper is to raise awareness for the necessity of ecological education. Environmental problems are urgent and must be addressed by the entire community, and education must be an integral part of the solution. Divergent opinions regarding the state of the environment, the consequences of its degradation and the role of education are good topics for discussion and debate. Also, environmental education should not force people to think a certain way, it can help people learn how to think – including how to solve problems, make decisions, weigh options and align values with personal actions.

Through a European Parliament Report from the not-too-distant past, the European Union was asked to provide all the instruments and all the Community legislation to contribute to the conservation of natural resources and the continuation of sustainable development, both in the Union and outside it.

It is appreciated from this level that environmental education should be a component of elementary education, and consumers and producers should be involved in the sustainable use of natural resources.

Conclusion: Environmental education is a process that aims to improve the quality of life by providing people with the "tools" they need to solve and prevent environmental problems. Environmental education can help people gain the knowledge, skills, motivations, values and commitment they need to effectively manage the earth's resources and take responsibility for maintaining the quality of the environment.

Keywords: ecological, education, environment, urgency.

SECTION B: NON-REFUNDABLE PROJECTS

Moderator:

Mr. Robert MINCULESCU – County Center for Resources and
Educational Assistance Arges

Technical College “Costin D. Nenițescu” Pitesti- Leader in the Implementation of European Projects

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Objectives: Presenting “Costin D. Nenițescu” Technical College from Pitesti as it has distinguished itself in the last 25 years of existence of the European Union Program for education, training, youth and sport– Erasmus+ both at National and European level by outstanding results achieved in our students’ vocational training during internships carried out in other European countries.

The school unit holds the Excellence Award granted by the National Agency for the Community Programs in Vocational Education and Training for the quality of the implemented projects, received the first VET Mobility Charter in Romania (Recognition of Quality in European Project Management) for the period 2015-2020 and in 2021 it received a new VET Charter for the period 2021-2027 (Vet Accreditation Code Erasmus+2020-1-RO01-KA120-VET-095208). Thus, 300 students and 30 teachers STAFF will take part in training periods in Europe. The main partners of the school are: Berufskolleg Uerdingen, Krefeld - Germany, SBG - Sachsische Bildungsgesellschaft fur Umweltschutz und Chemieberufe Dresden mbH Dresden, Dresden - Germany, WBS Training - Dresden -branch, Germany, Braga Training Center MOB, Portugal.

Another result is an improvement in the quality of training services offered by the beneficiary institution. By disseminating the results of the project, it was planned to use the materials resulting from the practical activities carried out to create a portfolio and a methodological guide for the specialized modules. These teaching materials are integrated into the learning process. Demonstration classes were organized, during which new training techniques and methods were presented, adapted and integrated into the didactic process from our school, contributing to increase the quality of initial vocational training services in the beneficiary institution.

Participation in European Vocational Training Projects brings added value to personal development which increases the participants’ chances of integration into the labor market as a result of the new knowledge, skills and competences acquired, certified by the documents received, especially the European Mobility Certificate.

Keywords: partnership, projects, expertise, Erasmus+

CUT! Preventing alcohol abuse among preadolescents

(1) Cosmin Mazilescu
(1) Școala Gimnazială Băiculești, Băiculești, Jud. Argeș

Pre-adolescents (age 11-14) and young people are a population particularly at risk of alcohol abuse, as it is often perceived as a means of acceptance within the group. From a psychological point of view, the use and abuse of alcohol among pre-adolescents is often triggered by underlying factors related to identity building, acceptance by the group, conformity with the mainstream, fear of exclusion, bullying, rites of passage, challenging the authority etc. Pre-adolescence is also characterised by an increased use of electronic devices (e.g. smartphones, computers, videogames), internet-based services (e.g. social media, the Internet, internet based videogames, etc.) and an increased autonomy in their family and social life, all factors that play a role in shaping young people's minds.

Objectives:

Specific objectives include:

- Raise awareness on the issue of alcohol abuse
- Prevent risky behaviors eventually leading to alcohol abuse
- Develop response strategies to tackle the issue of alcohol abuse among pre-adolescents

Materials and methods: focus discussion groups and mobility actions in Poland and Italy (Milan) for 20 children and 2 teachers.

Expected results:

The main project deliverables include:

- CUT! Video Series
- CUT! Practical Guide
- CUT! Lessons Learned and Policy Recommendations Report
- A training course involving 7 participants from the partners' countries is organized by AIDD – “Associazione Italiana contro la Diffusione del Disagio giovanile” in order to: promote the use of the intellectual outputs; provide the end users with the competences and information concerning the theme of alcohol abuse among students.

Conclusion: The project is now in the phase of interviewing for setting recommendations and politics for the European Committee in order to reduce alcohol consumption among pre-adolescents.

Keywords: prevention, pre-adolescents, alcohol consumption.

Impact study on The National School Dropout Reduction Program in Romania (PNRAS)

Merișani Secondary School

by Florina Diana Negreanu (learning support teacher - County Center of Resources and Educational Assistance/ CJRAE)

and Cristiana-Raluca Iordache (English teacher at “George Ștephănescu” Arefu Secondary School)

In the educational unit Merișani Secondary School, in the 2020-2021 school year, there was a dropout rate of 4%. At the same time, referring to the same school year, there is an 86% graduation rate for the 8th grade. Of the 86% who graduated from secondary school, only 78% participated in the National Evaluation. We found out that a very large percentage (46%) of the 78% who signed up for the National Evaluation, obtained marks below 6.

The **beneficiaries of the project** are secondary school students (126 students, aged between 11 and 16 years old), because the risk of dropping out is higher in secondary education, especially in the 5th grade, which represents the transition year from primary to secondary school.

Following a SWOT analysis carried out together with the team of teachers in the school, we identified the problems faced by the students of the secondary school:

- Increased abandonment rate;
- Low graduation rate;
- Low participation rate in the National Evaluation.

The **objectives** of the project are:

- Reducing the number of students who are at risk of dropping out of school by offering them items necessary for the schooling process;
- Stimulating the academic improvement of teachers through training sessions to develop alternative teaching skills;
- Increasing the graduation rate of the secondary education cycle by organizing school activities related to the curricular area;
- Increasing the percentage of students enrolled in the National Evaluation through motivational and alternative learning activities.

The **expected results** following the implementation of the project activities are:

- Reducing the risk of school dropout, to at least 10%, among the students in our school who are in the target group;
- Improving the results obtained in the National Evaluation by the students of the target group in our school;
- Increasing the percentage of students in the target group who complete secondary education.

Keywords: school dropout, complete education, society, integration.

”COMPETENȚE EUROPENE DOBÂNDITE ÎN TIMPUL STAGIILOR DE PREGĂTIRE PRACTICĂ”

”European Skills Acquired During Practical Training Sessions”

project nr. 2023-1-RO01KA122-VET-000121012, in the fields of Education and Training, within Key Action 1 - KA 122 VET, ERASMUS+

Irina Drăgălău(1), Iuliana Maria Bădicioiu(2), Elena Cențiu(3), Corina Dinu(4)

(1,2,3,4) ”Armand Călinescu” Technical College of Pitești

Programme Operator: National Agency for Community Programmes in the Field of Vocational Education and Training (ANPCDEFP);

Source of the Grant: European Economic Area Grants;

Field of application: Vocational Education and Training;

Partners: EUIESA –INTERNATIONAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP SUSTAINABILITY ASSOCIATION;

Objectives: participants’ personal and professional development to support future-oriented education and training, flexibility for the labor market, perfecting knowledge, skills and attitudes in the field of food service, enriching civic and cultural skills. Participation can make it easier to get a job in companies from Romania or abroad, based on Europass Mobility document. Participation will bring benefits to activities students will be involved in later (competitions, celebrations, exams, volunteering) due to the positive impact and professional development.

Other students in the school will be motivated to learn for their own selection in future projects. Employers will prefer hiring our graduates due to their practical experience. This project will make our school become recognized locally and regionally as a high quality education and service provider.

Management details: Approved budget 44,246 Euro. Time 12 months (18/09/2023-17/09/2024)

Activities approved: VET;

Results (Expected): Issuing 14 Europass Mobility documents, 14 certificates of participation, 14 portfolios, 14 Learning Agreements, 14 Language certificates. Increasing the professional, civic, cultural and linguistic training of the participants. Entrepreneurship development, improvement of initiative and team work, increasing self-esteem. Writing a magazine with the Practical Activities carried out in Portugal, the 031625 project’s website, Facebook page and illustrative panel. A significant increase of the number of younger students registering for Chef and Gastronomy Technician qualifications in our school.

Volunteering Project “TOGETHER”

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- (2) Ciucă Emilia Rodica
- (3) Florescu Florina Laura
- (4) Lungu Mihaela
- (5) Botaș Silviu Cătălin
- (6) Dumitru Elisabeta Veluța
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The doctors and nurses from the Neuromotor Recovery Section from the Pediatric Hospital in Pitești observed that the children admitted claim psychological discomfort of all levels, from mild anxiety to panic attacks and generalized anxiety and all these symptoms are staying in the way of their recovery. The school counselors from the County Center for Resources and Educational Assistance Argeș were invited to provide psychological counseling for the young patients and their families.

Objectives: The main objective of the volunteering project is to offer psychological assistance and speech therapy sessions to the patients (children and their parents) from the Neuromotor Recovery Section from the Pediatric Hospital of Pitești, Romania. The duration of the project is for one school year, starting from September 2023 to June 2024.

Materials and methods: Cognitive-behavioral therapy; play therapy (different games, toys, paper and colored pencils); speech therapy, clinical hypnosis.

Results: It has been observed that, during several sessions, the children that benefited from the therapy sessions improved their resilience to long-term treatments. Some of the children are dealing with physical pain that can become unbearable, therefore the psychological support turns out to be really helpful.

Conclusions: A number of 40 school counselors and speech therapists from the County Center for Resources and Educational Assistance Argeș offered as volunteers for this project. Every week 1 counselor and 1 speech therapist are going to the Neuromotor Recovery Section from the Pediatric Hospital of Pitești, providing assistance where needed.

Keywords: psychological support, long-term treatment, resilience.

TOMORROW'S LEADERS: FOSTERING ACTIVE CITIZENSHIP THROUGH EDUCATION

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Abstract:

Objectives: The purpose of this paper is to introduce educational tools developed to enhance the awareness and skills of young Europeans in active citizenship. All indicators point to the conclusion that Romanians lack the ability, will, and capacity to recognize anti-social attitudes and behaviors, despite the educational system taking steps to promote active citizenship as a general concept.

Considering active citizenship behavior as an extension of a society's beliefs and a vital factor for fostering positive attitudes, the project 'Citizens in Action' — ERASMUS-JMO-2021-OFET-NET-101048265 — aims to create user-friendly educational tools for schools that are attractive to students, even at a young age.

EU funding, previously limited to universities but now available for schools under the 'Jean Monnet in other fields of Education and Training: Networks' scheme, keeps a research-university component.

3 training courses were created:

- Course on gender equality
- Course on European landscape
- Course on Europe and European institutions

Target group: 20 students from each partner school

Partners in the project: schools from Romania, Italy, Latvia and Greece

The Romanian partner: Micesti Elementary School, Arges county

Activities approved: transnational meetings, intellectual outputs, multiplier events, students' trip to Bruxelles in 2024.

Conclusions: An active citizenship attitude is a necessary condition to achieve growth and social cohesion. In a world often found on the verge of conflicts, the future leaders, whether of communities or countries, need to be raised with positive attitudes and correct values.

Keywords: active citizenship, innovative education tools, positive attitude, EU.

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